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[➤ https://www.fao.org/fsnforum/call-submissions/addressing-governance-agrifood-systems-transformation](https://www.fao.org/fsnforum/call-submissions/addressing-governance-agrifood-systems-transformation)

Call for submissions:

How can FAO better support countries in addressing governance of agrifood systems transformation to make them more sustainable, inclusive and resilient?

Collection of contributions received

The Call for Submissions “[How can FAO better support countries in addressing governance of agrifood systems transformation to make them more sustainable, inclusive and resilient?](#)” was held on the FAO Global Forum on Food Security and Nutrition platform from 8 February to 1 April 2024. The call was available in Arabic, Chinese, English, French, Russian and Spanish.

This Call was organized jointly by the Office of SDGs, the Agrifood Systems and Food Safety Division, the Governance and Policy Support Unit, and the Development Law Service, to engage various stakeholders and gather examples of governance-related measures and interventions with transformative impact for agrifood systems. The results emerging from the submissions will contribute to informing FAO’s work with governments and other stakeholders related to policy, law, and governance for more inclusive, resilient, and sustainable agrifood systems.

This call received **88 valuable contributions** from experts, representing diverse public, CSOs and private organizations and working in different fields of expertise around a globe. In particular, participants located in **48 countries**:

Argentina, Bangladesh, Belgium, Bolivia, Brazil, Cameroon, Chad, Chile, Congo, Costa Rica, Czechia, Ecuador, Ethiopia, France, Gabon, Ghana, Germany, Ireland, Indonesia, India, Iran, Italy, Jordan, Kenya, Lebanon, Liberia, Mauritania, Mexico, Nepal, Nigeria, Netherlands, Pakistan, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Philippines, Saudi Arabia, Senegal, South Africa, Sri Lanka, Syrian Arab Republic, Sweden, Togo, Turkey, United Arab Emirates, Uganda, UK, and USA.

This document is the Proceedings report on the Call for Submissions that includes the topic note, the names of participants with the links to the original submissions, and the content of all contributions in English inserted in a chronological manner.

Table of Contents

Topic note.....	5
Contributions received	9
1. FAO's joint team (DDCG, ESF, LEG, and OSG), FAO, Italy	9
2. Elsie Moore, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, United States of America	9
3. Christiane Monsieur, FAO, Italy	13
4. Francisco Minuche, Ministerio de Agricultura y Ganadería, Ecuador	23
5. Repa Kustipia, Center for Study Indonesian Food Anthropology (CS-IFA) & Social Enterprise Gastro Tourism Academy, Indonesia	28
6. Viola Taormina, University of Foggia, Italy	34
7. Balan Sundarakani, University of Wollongong in Dubai, United Arab Emirates	39
8. Ranjitha Kumar, IT for Change, India	42
9. MATCHAYAM Marie Goretti, University of Yaoundé 1, Cameroon	49
10. Lizzy Igbine, Nigerian women agro allied farmers association, Nigeria	51
11. Kibrom Fesseha Tesfay, University of politecnico di Torino, Ethiopia	54
12. Julio Prudencio, Investigador independiente afiliado a la Fundación TIERRA y al Instituto de Investigaciones Socioeconómicas de la Universidad Católica de Bolivia, Bolivia (Plurinational State of) 60	
13. Patti Rundall, IBFAN, United Kingdom	61
14. James Mawanda, Foundation for Climate Health Solutions, Uganda	66
15. Institute of Food Technologists, Institute of Food Technologists, United States of America	68
16. Luis Lobo, FAO, Chile	69
17. Gwynne Foster, South Africa	74
18. Raugathe Crucis Arcturus BOULINGUI, RADDEV, Congo	81
19. Santosh Kumar Mishra, Population Education Resource Centre, Department of Lifelong Learning and Extension, India	84
20. Peetambar Dahal, University of California, Davis, USA, United States of America	90
21. Jograj Giri, Association of Family Forest Owners, Nepal (AFFON), Nepal	91
22. Dhanbahadur Magar, krishi journal, Nepal	94
23. Samantha Kumarasena, National Cleaner Production Centre, Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka	103
24. Vijaya Khader, Acharya N. G. Ranga Agricultural University, India	107
25. Essohouna Manzi-Nika Bakoussam, BOAEC Sarl, Togo	113
26. Adanela MUSARAJ, CNRS, France	117
27. Nazimi Acikgoz, Ege University, Turkey	125
28. Sara Burrone, FAO, Italy	125
29. Bibi Ally, Private Sector Mechanism of UN Committee on Food Security, United States of America	129
30. Bhavani R Vaidyanathan, India	132
31. Dioguen Zaridze, FAO, Italy	133

There's also the possibility for the producer to have access to the market price, in order to make a stand against corrupted merchants.
Finally, access to equipment to reduce the arduousness of farm work.

15. What are your key messages/takeaways from this intervention/measure?

See the project report

16. Please feel free to share relevant links to resources and documentation regarding your intervention.

[Project "appui au développement de la filière céréale au Togo"—Google search](#)

26. [Adanela MUSARAJ, CNRS, France](#)

One of the most popular perspectives in the agricultural sector is that of resource conservation, such as habitat or the proper management of basic resources like land and water. However, in recent years, there has been a trend towards combining this more ecological perspective of agriculture with socioeconomic factors and, in general, with a multidimensional perspective. Exploring such new perspectives is the aim of this contribution . These studies deserve a great deal of attention, but it is also clear that research at farm level is not enough, due to the fact that there are factors determined by political matters or others influenced by the socioeconomic environment of the farming system, e.g. productive activities surrounding to agriculture.

See the attachments:

- [FSN Forum Musaraj Contribution](#)

Template for submissions

- **Proponent (name/institution/unit)**

Dr. Adanela Musaraj, European University Institute, STG

2. Title of the example presented and the type of *governance-related* transformative intervention/measure (policy, legal, institutional, financial...)

Analytical assessment of environmental, economic and social dimensions on Farming System in Western Balkans

3. Location of the transformative intervention/measure (global/regional/national/sub-national; urban/rural)

Regional: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Kosovo * and Serbia

4. Which aspect, problem or challenge of the agrifood system was the transformative intervention/measure aiming to address?

The growing abundance of studies focused on the evaluation of sustainability in general and of agriculture in particular stems from the need for balanced actions to face the challenges of modern-day society, which are usually grouped into environmental, economic and social terms. Consequently, measuring sustainability is without question a multi-attribute and holistic issue involving numerous variables, which at the same time tend to be interrelated. This has led some authors to believe that a precise measurement is impossible as it is a specific concept for each place while also being dynamic, and it will depend, in general, on the perspective of the analysis. The complexity of this issue derives from both the ambiguity of the concept of sustainability itself and the scale of the field of study. On one hand, for example, one of the most popular perspectives in the agricultural sector is that of resource conservation, such as habitat or the proper management of basic resources like land and water. However, in recent years, there has been a trend towards combining this more ecological perspective of agriculture with socioeconomic factors and, in general, with a multidimensional perspective. On the other hand, study methods are quite diverse, often depending on whether an analysis is being conducted at an aggregate level or if the study is dealing in microeconomic terms. Most of the internationally standardized indicators use an aggregate or macroeconomic approach, e.g. Pressure-State-Response (PSR), Driving Forces-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR), Flexible Framework for Indicators for Sustainability in Regions using Systems Dynamics Modelling (INSURE), etc. Nevertheless, more specific analyses focus on sustainability at farm level, fundamentally because it is believed that individual farmers are responsible for making the most important decisions concerning use of resources and implementation of techniques and technologies. These studies deserve a great deal of attention, but it is also clear that research at farm level is not enough, due to the fact that there are factors determined by political matters or others influenced by the socioeconomic environment of the farming system, e.g. productive activities surrounding to agriculture. In general, the numerous studies carried out in this field reveal a wide range of indicators, many of which are susceptible to standardized application or are applied to other contexts with the specific adaptations of the analysis objectives and the particular characteristics of the activities or farming systems being studied. However, one of the least analyzed issues, and one which incites great interest, is the determination of interrelationships and interdependences among said indicators.

5. What transformational impact was the intervention/measure aiming to achieve (including in terms of the three pillars of sustainability)?

The aim of this paper is to conduct an analysis of sustainability indicators and their interrelationships. The object of study is the farming system in Western Balkan Countries, characterized by a structure consisting of small-scale farmers. These growers use technologies adapted to the environmental conditions of the area (such as limited basic resources) and they have also fostered socioeconomic growth in the region thanks to a farming system which currently includes the participation of numerous marketing, auxiliary, and service companies. Furthermore, the development of this farming system has been described as a process of interrelationships between different economic, social and environmental components, without which its success would not have been possible.

6. What was the impact achieved in practice?

The results reveal that the increase in the economic and social indicators reduces environmental pressures on the use of resources; in parallel, it can also be observed how social and environmental improvements reveal positive effects on the economic dimension of the farmers. Overall, this study presents an analytical study that combines indicators at farm level and the effects related to the productive activities surrounding agriculture.

7. How was the transformative change obtained by the intervention/measure? (a) data and evidence collected, b) concrete ways to measure, c) actors involved)

The methodology utilized in this study corresponds to an analysis of simple indexes following the SAFE method - Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment, while the methodology applied for the construction of synthetic indexes is the AHP method – Analytical Hierarchy Process. Taking these as the basis, an interrelationship analysis is conducted by means of a system of simultaneous equations that treat the endogeneity of the synthetic indicators of sustainability. The estimation of interrelationships is carried out by means of a multivariate analysis, considering the indigeneity between the sustainability dimensions and the influence of several features of the agro-food system. In the present paper an analysis is carried out based on surveys of local actors over a shorter time period, but done for more recent years with the aim of evaluating the previously-mentioned multidimensional interrelationships.

1. Indicators Selection and Construction of Synthetic Indicators

As stated above, the selection of simple or individual indicators will be performed by using the SAFE analytical framework for reference. In this way, with the general objective of assessing the sustainability of agriculture by integrating environmental, economic and social dimensions, the analysis follows the hierarchical structure of principles, criteria and indicators. The principles constitute the first level and are the general conditions considered to achieve sustainability from a multidimensional point of view; the criteria represent the resulting states when the principles are respected; and the indicators are the variables, whether they are quantitative or qualitative, which can be evaluated in relation to a criterion. The established criteria and, in particular, the indicators were selected mostly after taking into account various sustainability analyses of the

farming system being studied, as well as analyses of agricultural sectors in different regions of Western Balkans, previously indicated. The indicators are Water usage by land area, Water usage per ton of product, Nitrogen balance, Phytosanitary products usage, Amount of waste by land area, Private profitability of farm, Labor productivity, Gross value added, Percentage of income from subsidies, Total employment, transfer of farm to children or family descendants, Family and fixed labor, Income dependent on agriculture, Participation in professional associations and cooperatives.

This methodological context allows for the calculation of synthetic indicators or indexes, with the objective of also reducing the number of variables in the subsequent causality analyses from a multidimensional point of view. This technique of indicator aggregation has also been widely utilized in sustainability analyses. However, this method is not exempt from difficulties derived from the subjectivity and incommensurability of the components of sustainable development. Consequently, there are several implementation methods which attempt to overcome said drawbacks, leading to phases in which alternative techniques are applied. Those that require more transparent attention are the data standardization phase and the weight designation and aggregation phase. On the one hand, the aim of the standardization phase is to facilitate the comparison of analysis units, which in this case are the individual indicators according to the principles and criteria described. The selection of one technique or another will depend on the characteristics of each indicator and will partially determine the expert assessment of the analyst. Among the mostly widely used are z-score standardization and Min–Max scaling. The former, Z-score, is advisable specially when analyzing a large number of elements (large sample size), when the minimum and maximum are unknown or there are atypical extreme values (outliers) that advise against

the use of Min–Max standardization. However, in the present work, the latter is the technique that is followed, precisely as suggested by the SAFE framework.

On the other hand, there are also different techniques for the phases involving designation of weights and aggregation, and they can be grouped into two general types (OECD 2008):

i) statistic or positive based on designating weights implicitly using statistical analysis of the database obtained from indicators, of which the most common are regressions, Principle Components Analysis (PCA), factorial analysis, and Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA);

ii) participatory or normative, usually based on weights designated with the advice of experts, the most common of which are swing weighting, the SMART method, and the Analytic Hierarchy Process, AHP. This second type of methods, in spite of having been discarded for possessing a certain level of subjectivity, provides an order or ranking, which might be more in agreement with the social preferences on the dimensions of sustainability. We therefore continue in this case with the AHP technique, considered to be a structured and flexible means for making decisions in a multicriteria context. This technique has been utilized in numerous empirical applications for decision making and the construction of synthetic indexes in the agricultural sector. With the aim of applying the above method, this study was conducted with a panel of experts: civil servants from Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries from every country of Western Balkans, civil servants from the Ministry of Environment of corresponding countries, and 18 university researches in the fields of agricultural sustainability who are specialists in the subjects of socio-economic, environmental sciences, and agricultural engineering, respectively, but who are not implicated in the study.

2. Interrelationships Among Indicators

One of the main aims of this study is to make progress in causality methods using multi-equation models to detect possible synergy effects among sustainability dimensions. This can be done employing linear simultaneous equation systems. The variables regarding the agricultural system were formulated based on farmer evaluations of other activities and on general data of the system itself:

- Local consulting in new technology, biological control and organic farming, LCTB, measured as the percentage of total consulting per farm, obtained from the surveys.
- Concentration index of supplying resources enterprises, AAX, aggregate variable for each growing season estimated using the Hirschman-Herfindahl, which is an indicator of diversification in the sector and also utilized as an indicator of agglomeration of activities surrounding agriculture.
- Indicator of assessment of the auxiliary industry, VAX, standardized variable measured by means of a weighting from 1 to 5 included in the survey of farmers.
- Indicator of environmental performance in the marketing sector, MENV, measured as an aggregate variable, following the methodologies of works related specifically to this farming system. This is included as a factor indicative of the environmental spillover effect in this horticultural sector.
- Indicator of assessment of local financing mechanisms, VLF, standardized variable measured by means of a weighting from 1 to 5 included in the survey of farmers.
- Indicator of assessment of research centers specialized in the sector, VRD, standardized variable also measured by means a weighting from 1 to 5 included in the survey of farmers.
- Indicator of internationalization of the sector, EXP, measured according to the export intensity (aggregate variable for each growing season) following the methodology of work on this farming system by OECD, and included as a factor of a possible influence of stricter sustainability requirements by international markets.

On the other hand, in order to proceed to said simultaneous estimations we must assume the normality of the variables considered. To this end, they need to undergo transformations, for example, with the Box-

Cox method, which allows an approximation to normality. Finally, there is a wide variety of estimation methods, among which are the Generalized Moments Methods (GMM), and estimation by means instrumental variables, which includes Two Stage Least Squares (2SLS) and Three Stage Least Squares (3SLS).

These approximations are utilized and have been applied in a productivity-environmental interrelationships analysis for Western Balkans fruit and vegetable sector. Prior to estimating the equations system, we proceeded to analyze the correlation coefficients of the variables in order to avoid multicollinearity and correlation with the error terming the estimations. To corroborate this, the variance inflation factor was also calculated. Endogeneity tests using the Wu-Hausman test were also conducted previously for each of the proposed equations.

The results indicated the existence of endogeneity bias (p-value b 0.05 of Wu-Hausman F test) and the necessity to utilize instrumental variables. In this way, the proposed simultaneous equations system with synthetic indexes is estimated following the method of two-stage least squares (2SLS). It is essentially an estimator of instrumental variables that utilizes estimated endogenous variables (in first stage with ordinary least squares, OLS) and a vector of explanatory or predetermined variables as instruments. In order to have a wide range of possible instruments, other predetermined variables were also considered: Size measured by the land area in hectares of the farm; the annual investment in Technological improvement, also obtained from the data surveys; and lagged Export produce ratio, measured as the average export sales ratio of the sector in the three growing seasons prior to the period of study, considering the increase of exports during the last years in this farming system.

Taking into consideration the number of explanatory variables, drawback of over-identified equations is encountered, i.e. there are more predetermined variables than endogenous variables, requiring the use of linear combinations of said variables to determine vectors X_1 , X_2 and X_3 , one for each synthetic index. The validity of the instruments in each estimation was tested using the Sargan test. Furthermore, a panel of fixed effects data was considered and 2 dummy variables were introduced (corresponding to the two last seasons) to capture the possible time effects; nevertheless, both effects are tested with Snedecor's F-distribution test. Also, testing for heteroscedasticity is carried out with the Breusch and Pagan test (B-P). Subsequently, the estimation of the equations system was carried out using the method of Three-Stage Least Squares (3SLS), which allows optimizing estimation in the presence of possible correlations between the error terms of simultaneous equations.

8. What were the key challenges and trade-offs identified and how did a measure/intervention succeed in producing co-benefits and synergies [delivering on economic, environmental and social (including gender equality) sustainability] rather than favoring one option over the other?

The results show a positive or synergy effects among said dimensions, evaluating the influence of specific factors related to the agri-food system in said interrelationships.

9. Who were the key actors and stakeholders involved in the design and implementation of the intervention/measures in question, and what were their respective roles and capacities to exert power and influence?

The study of sustainability of the Western Balkans fruit and vegetable system from a holistic perspective has made it necessary to resort to a vast array of data collection techniques, both primary and secondary. Primary type information has been gathered mainly by conducting surveys on farms. In this case an ad hoc questionnaire was created for the present study. This survey features a variety of questions with the

objective of obtaining basic information about: general farm data such as the degree of integration with cooperatives and farming organizations; environmental issues; social and economic details; and other information related to connections with the service sector and other auxiliary activities linked to the farming. The surveys were conducted during three different periods with the purpose of obtaining information for the 2020–2011, 2021–2022 and 2022–2023 growing seasons. The selection of the sample was stratified according to the local division of the province's vegetable producing area bearing in mind that the former accounts for 72.2% of the farms and the latter the remaining 27.8%. For each stratum the farms were selected by simple random sample, without replacement, carrying out a total of 340 surveys; however, several measurement errors were detected, which brought down the final sample to 319 farms. In general, relative homogeneity was detected among the farms surveyed, specifically in terms of family ownership (96.2%) and land area, which was between 1 and 5 ha, with an average of 2.19 ha. Albeit that the number of surveys varied between the areas studied, the variance analysis (ANOVA tests) on specific metric variables (gross value added per hectare, water and fertilizer usage, and number of workers) did not cause significant differences, which is way no distinction was made according to location. Other data on the sector were obtained from secondary sources. Information related to cooperatives and marketing was gathered from works on productivity, yield, and environmental management by INSTAT and annual reports published by the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Rural Development of each country. Data related to the auxiliary industry and services were provided mainly by the annual reports of Chambers of Commerce of each country. Other socio-economic data were taken from statistics provided by the National Statistics Institute, and the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Rural Development of the corresponding countries.

10. Did any of these key actors and stakeholders oppose or resist the envisioned transformative intervention, and if so, what were their main motivations and interests, and how was this resistance addressed?

None of the key actors nor the stakeholders resisted to the proposed interventions. The participation was 100%.

11. To what extent is this measure transformative in improving the livelihoods of the most disadvantaged, and how does it contribute to a more inclusive food system?

Most of the internationally standardized indicators for the evaluation of sustainability in general and of agriculture in particular stems from the need for balanced actions to face the challenges of modern-day society, use an aggregate or macroeconomic approach, e.g. Pressure-State-Response (PSR), Driving Forces-Pressure-State-Impact- Response (DPSIR), Flexible Framework for Indicators for Sustainability in Regions using Systems Dynamics Modelling (INSURE), etc. This study aims to contribute to the collection of empirical studies on sustainability from two perspectives: a) the microeconomic analysis at farm level and the influence of several factors of the agri-food system; b) the analysis of interrelationships among components of sustainability. For this topic, study methods are quite diverse, often depending on whether an analysis is being conducted at an aggregate level or if the study is dealing in microeconomic terms. These studies deserve a great deal of attention, but it is also clear that research at farm level is not enough

12. What means were used to demonstrate positive changes in the most disadvantaged sectors of the population, and what monitoring and accountability mechanisms were put in place to ensure proper implementation?

In regards to the variables included as predetermined, it is worth mentioning that the results of the variables related to the farm characteristics show a positive effect of organic farming and biological control (BIO) on not only reducing environmental pressures and improving the management of resources, but also on the economic and social indexes. As mentioned earlier, this is related to the product specialization along these lines (organic produce) which has occurred in both farming practices and marketing over the last decades. Furthermore, these are significantly influenced by the adaptation index (ADI), which highlights the capabilities of the family structure to deal with the changes in this sector; however, the yield per hectare (YLH) only has a positive effect on the economic variable and, to a lesser extent, on the social variable. As for the assessments and general structure of the sector, the results reveal the importance of a cluster of auxiliary services and industries built around the farming system. There is a positive impact of local consulting (LCTB) on matters of technological improvements and organic production for all of the dimensional indicators; the agglomeration index of the input supply firms (AAX) only shows a positive effect on the economic variables, although the assessment of these companies (VAX) has significant positive impacts on the economic and social dimensions; an environmental spillover effect is also detected, by the significant effect that the environmental performance of marketing firms (MENV) has on the reduction of environmental pressures and the improvement of resources management; regarding the existence of local financing services (VLF), it has positive effects from a socioeconomic point of view; there is also significant influence from research centers specializing in the sector (VRD) on the environmental and economic indicators; and, finally, the export ratio (EXP), in concurrence with other specific studies on this issue has a positive effect in that it reduces environmental pressures and improves the socioeconomic indicators.

13. Key lessons that can be learned from your case (both positive and negative) and whether these could be applicable in other contexts with similar characteristics

In the case of this study on the Western Balkans farming system, the SAFE framework has been utilized as reference for the elaboration of a series of principles, criteria and indicators with the aim of conducting a bottom-up analysis. By doing so, the farmers are considered as the principle decision-makers in matters of environmental sustainability, and, at the same time, as those who are influenced by the social and economic context of their production activity. Albeit that initially no specific concept of sustainability was taken into consideration, this article focused on the holistic nature of the issue and on the existence, or lack thereof, of synergy or positive effects in the multidimensional relationships in order to achieve a suitable evaluation of sustainability. The statistical-econometric analysis, based on the dimensional aggregation (synthetic indexes) of the individual indicators of sustainability, and the assessment of the possible relationships of endogeneity have combined to provide a range of evidences on the positive crossed effects among the various environmental, economic and social components. Although a more evident interrelationship is observed from a social-economic point of view, the results obtained also reveal that the reduction of pressures on natural resources is influenced in such a way that the economic and social indicators are improved. Moreover, the results also show that there are increases in the economic indicators, along with an improved social index, better resources management and the reduction of pressures on the environment. Additionally, there is evidence among these interrelationships of the influence of certain characteristics associated with the structure and activity of the farms such as the implementation of biological pest control techniques, organic production, and the farm adaptation indicators. Particularly interesting results were also obtained for the impact of the characteristics and the assessment of marketing firms and other companies, as well as the service sector. These are reflected by the significant effects of specialized local consulting services, local financing mechanisms, research centers, and internationalization in marketing. A number of limitations of the empirical study can be cited. Firstly, it was based on a series of indicators using a sample of farms and certain data regarding the socioeconomic context as its primary sources of reference. Secondly, the data correspond to a reduced period of time. Despite these shortcomings, specific evidences were obtained of interrelationships among

dimensions of sustainability. Furthermore, from a methodological point of view, the authors believe that new methods are provided for conducting a more thorough analysis of agrarian systems, not only considering the components of sustainability of farms, but also viewing several activities around their activity. Nevertheless, future works could be aimed at studying these interrelationships systems in greater depth; for example, the family farms-marketing firms-service industry, and the links with other social and environmental factors in the sector. Finally, we believe that any political implications derived from the present study must be based mainly on this holistic perspective and on the importance of specific actions oriented towards strengthening the management of natural resources and activities in the socioeconomic context. The results obtained may show the importance of agrifood systems with a clear family component as well as the development of cooperatives and other services linked to the sector that could explain the resilience and good performance showed by several indicators, all of which could explain the resilience and good performance as illustrated by several indicators.

14. Based on your experience, what gaps/areas of improvement still remain that need further action?

Sustainability of farming activity is currently one of the main concerns of analysts and policy makers involved in regional development. Nevertheless, it is well known that this is a complex issue, primarily due to the diversity and ambiguity of its conceptualization, not to mention the existence of multiple influential and interrelated variables. Despite the complexity of this subject, the development of numerous analytical frameworks in recent decades is a testament to the importance of conducting research on sustainability for the sake of decision making and fostering specialized political initiatives.

15. What are your key messages/takeaways from this intervention/measure?

While certain methodologies have proposed relative standardization and generalized application, the diversity of spatial and temporal scales imply the existence of a range of ways to approach said analyses, which in many cases are related to the objectives of the studies themselves or the innate characteristics of the field. Furthermore, the evaluation of the interrelationships among the components of sustainability is a significant matter which has not been sufficiently addressed. Although the results show synergies or evidence of complementarity among the economic, social and environmental dimensions, this may only indicate that adequate progress is being made in terms of sustainability objectives; however, these objectives, from a normative perspective, are never likely to have a clearly defined limit and require continual improvement. Thus, policy programs should encourage certain capabilities that promote these goals and should be more than simply an approach based on traditional subsidies for farms. For instance, they should be aimed at promoting a local services cluster, financing systems and specialized research, particularly those designed to improve the use of resources or organic production. These also include any actions that improve the adaptability (e.g. education, intergenerational transfer of farms, etc.) of the main actors in the farming system, which can have a significant impact on agricultural sustainability.

16. Please feel free to share relevant links to resources and documentation regarding your intervention.